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Oral communication (O17)

Novaterra project: Increasing sustainability in viticulture using novel fertilization and management strategies

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World population current predictions indicate that by 2100 the world population will reach 11 billion people from the current 8 billion. Supplying enough and healthy food is a big challenge for humans in a context of climatic change, environmental degradation, resources depletion, inequality and geopolitical instability [1]. Maintaining current yields, decreasing fertilizer and biocidal inputs, improving soil health and ecosystems services, and contributing to climatic change mitigation are pressure factors to introduce alternative agronomic practices in agricultural production. The NOVATERRA project [2] aims to increase sustainability in vineyards and olive groves by means of *i*) reducing N-fertilization, using soil N-stabilizers and biostimulants and *ii*) introducing green covers and floral margins to mitigate erosive processes and increase biodiversity.

In a vineyard of D.O. Ribera del Duero located in Anguix (Burgos, Spain), various fertilization strategies were adopted in 2021: conventional mineral fertilization (IF), reduced N inputs (-30%) combined with a Nitrogen stabilizer (nitrapyrin, 300 g/L of active ingredient - Instinct®, Corteva, at a dose rate of 1//ha) (OP30), reduced N inputs (-40%) with the combined action of the Nitrogen stabilizer and a commercial biostimulant (OP40BIO) and control (CF) without any N-fertilization. At the same time, in a different plot, green covers were established between lines with different management strategies: spontaneous vegetation (NGC), seeding a grass cover of *Brachipodium distachyum* (SGC), seeding a mixture with floral species (10%) and grasses (90%) (FGC) and a control (CT) with bare soil as conventional management of the vineyard.

The soil in the farm is classified as Calcaric cambisol (Cm) according to FAO [3], with loamy sand texture; located at an altitude of 809 masl, mean temperature of 11.6 °C and mean annual rainfall 420 mm; the climate is classified as Mediterranean with dry summer (Csb) according Köppen; the vineyard has a plantation frame of 1.3 x 3 m, with *Vitis vinifera* cv. Tempranillo and 1103P rootstock. All the experiments were carried out with four replicates in which 20 vines/subplot were selected for monitoring. Different parameters related with plant health, grape and pruning production, and must quality, were determined in the fertilization experiment according to international standard methods [4]. Moreover, at the end of the harvest, composite samples of 5 soil cores per subplot were collected at two depths 0-20 and 20-40 cm from both experiments. Samples were sieved at 2 mm, and stored, frozen or at ambient temperature, until analysis of biological and chemical parameters, respectively [5].

One-way ANOVA test was performed after checking for normality and homogeneity of variances assumption; *post-hoc* Tukey's test was used to find significant differences between treatments ($p < 0.05$).

The results obtained in the experiment for fertilization strategies (Figure 1A) showed an increase in the production in both grapes and pruning, and a higher Ravaz's index in the case of OP30 treatment compared to IF, and a decrease of these values for OP40BIO treatment, but both without statistical significance. Figure 1B shows that the treatment IF displayed the highest value of Yeast Assimilable N (YAN), an important parameter in must quality, with values closer to 140 mg/L, which is considered the limit value to avoid nutrient limitation in the fermentation process [6]. This YAN value was lower for the treatment OP40BIO in which the 40% reduction in N inputs was not compensated by the introduction of Instinct® or the addition of a biostimulant. This consortium has been proven to promote plant growth, but it has a lack of N₂-fixing bacteria able to increase soil available N.

In the experiment for green cover strategies, both covers, SGC and FGC, were seeded in March 2021 at the start of spring and they were quickly established, even in the steepest area of the vineyard, prone to have important rainfall erosion processes. Covers were cut in June 2021 to avoid competition for water or nutrients and plant cuttings were left on the soil as a natural mulching agent. Soil analyses were made after harvest and an increase in the organic C content of the upper soil horizon was observed in both seeded covers (SGC and FGC) in contrast with tilled and unseeded lines and those with spontaneous cover (Figure 2), but without statistical significance. In contrast, biological soil properties, such as soil basal respiration (SBR), were increased with the introduction of seeded covers, mainly FGC treatment, in which a wide variety of grasses and floral plant species were introduced.

In the present year 2022, interrow lines of green covers strategies experiment were reseeded again, and additionally, floral mixture was also introduced in the field margins at the beginning of lines with the objective of increasing biological connectivity between seminatural and cropping areas of the

vineyard. Additionally, as part of project development, a third experiment has started combining the most promising previous results of fertilization and cover management: reduced fertilization (OP30) and floral cover (FGC). In this third experiment, interrow lines of CT and FGC treatments were divided introducing new subplots where the three fertilization strategies, CF, IF and OP30 were applied. New biological properties, such abundance and diversity of soil fauna and microbiota, and beneficial insects, including pollinators and natural enemies, are being monitored during 2022 and will be continued in 2023, trying to demonstrate the effectiveness of alternative management practices with biodiversity objectives in the Mediterranean vineyards.

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